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Maximizing the adsorption capacity of iron oxide nanocatalysts for the degradation of organic dyes

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Advanced oxidation processes can counteract the hazardous effects of polluted effluents in a highly efficient way, in many cases limited by the adsorption capacity of the nanocatalyst that depends on their size, internal structure and coating. Here, magnetic iron oxide nanocatalysts consisting on single core (SC), multicore (MC) and core-shell (CS) structures, stabilized with citrate and silica, have been evaluated for the degradation of anionic acid orange 8 (AO8) and cationic methylene blue (MB). It was observed that the adsorption is a limiting parameter, as expected in a mainly heterogeneous process involving molecular adsorption, reaction, and desorption at the catalyst surface. Thus, for the anionic dye, AO8, no degradation is observed by any of the nanocatalysts considering their negative surface charge. However, for MB loaded SC or CS nanocatalysts, highest degradation yields (almost 100% after 180 min at 90 °C) were achieved through a homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis in the case of SC and a pure heterogeneous process in the case of CS. MC presents the larger aggregate size due to the lack of coating and low surface charge, leading to poor capacity of adsorption and degradation. On the other hand, magnetic induction heating promotes the degradation of MB (up to ≈50%, respect to room temperature). The results show that iron oxide nanocatalysts through Fenton reactions are an

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interesting alternative for wastewater treatment considering also that iron is non-toxic and one of the most abundant elements on Earth and can be recovered simply by applying a magnetic field.

1. Introduction

The increase of severe environmental regulations and the attention over social and political aspects of environmental protection has consolidated all the research efforts on more sustainable processes and ways to overcome pollution [1]. These quality standards exhort the need to eliminate and reprocess hazardous pollutants of which recalcitrant compounds stand as a treat that demands other non-biological technologies for their treatment. Such technologies can be classified as separation techniques or methods that chemically destroy contaminants (e.g. advanced oxidation processes or AOPs) [2–5]. In the latter methods, organic pollutants are mineralized into carbon dioxide, water and other harmless products. Nevertheless, AOPs still present some drawbacks and questions that need to be addressed in order to fully benefit from their advantages. Within AOPs, Fenton reaction is today underlined by a significant number of researchers for the treatment of polluted effluents. Here, highly oxidative oxygen species (ROS) are formed through the addition of hydrogen peroxide to both iron (II) (Fenton process) and iron (III) (Fenton-like process) salts [6–8]. This by-product (ROS) results as an attractive oxidative system for organic pollutants during wastewater treatment considering also that iron is non-toxic and one of the most abundant elements on Earth.

Usually, these Fenton reactions can be carried out in homogeneous phase, but drawbacks like pH dependence, precipitation of iron hydroxides as sludge, complex recovery of the iron catalysts and high costs resulting from acidification of the water after treatment can be presented [7,9,10]. On the other hand, heterogeneous catalysis is a promising alternative for this kind of processes if the catalyst can be recovered and reused [11]. In this sense, iron oxide nanoparticles stand out as a promising catalyst, since in addition to providing the iron ions necessary for the reaction, they can be easily separated from the medium using an external magnet, regenerated and reused in successive operation cycles [12]. The efficiency of the nanoparticles in these processes will depend to a large extent on their physicochemical characteristics, such as surface area, pore size/volume ratio or crystalline structure.

Currently, numerous published works [8,13–15] refer to the catalytic decomposition of diverse organic pollutants using different nanoparticles and nanoalloys by means of Fenton processes. The adsorption capacity of different nanomaterials has been revealed as a key parameter to enhance Fenton oxidative processes for some organic dyes [16–20]. Moreover, in previous research we show the enhancement of catalytic degradation of organic dyes in real and model systems using magnetic nanoparticles by means of magnetic induction heating [21,22]. Here, the combined effect of the adsorption and inductive heating on the catalytic effect of magnetic nanoparticles in Fenton reactions is evaluated. For this purpose, cationic and anionic dyes were adsorbed on iron oxide nanoparticles with different coatings and particle sizes and their subsequent degradation by oxidative processes under alternating magnetic fields were analysed. The possible occurrence of heterogeneous and/or homogenous catalysis and the dependence of the efficiency of the magnetic field on the magnetic properties of the materials were also investigated.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemical reagents and analysis

Iron(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, >99%), iron(II) chloride tetrahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, >99%), citric acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$, >99%), octylphenoxypolyethoxyethanol (Igepal CA-630, 99%), tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS, 99%), ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , 30%), sodium

acetate (NaAc, $\geq 99\%$), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 , 35%), ethanol (99.8%), acid orange (AO8, 65%), methylene blue (MB) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. AO8 and MB molecular structure is shown in Fig. 1.

Colorimetric analyses were carried out to quantify the degradation yields of the organic dyes. UV/Visible spectrum for AO8 and MB, before and after treatments, was obtained using a Perkin-Elmer LAMBDA 35 UV-visible spectrophotometer (Waltham, MA, USA). Calibration curves as a function of the concentration at the maximum absorbance (489 and 663 nm for AO8 and MB, respectively), were performed using a Biochrom WPA Biowave DNA UV-visible spectrophotometer (Cambridge, UK). The calibration curve of dyes is shown in Fig. 1.

2.2. Synthesis of iron oxide nanocatalysts

2.2.1. Single core nanocatalyst

Single core iron oxide nanocatalyst (SC) was synthesized by coprecipitation of precursors. For this purpose, 5.18 mmol of FeCl_2 and 9.98 mmol of FeCl_3 were dissolved in 20 mL of water. Subsequently, a solution of 0.05 mol of NH_4OH and 0.07 mol of hydrazine was prepared in a volume of 50 mL. The solution of the precursors was added dropwise over the second one and the mixture was kept under reflux with stirring at 90 °C for 30 min.

In order to increase the stability of the obtained particles by coating them with citrate groups, 10 mL of a 0.2 M solution of citric acid was added to the suspension of particles previously synthesized. The mixture was kept for 90 min with stirring at 90 °C. The product was washed three times with acetone and finally dispersed in distillate water using sonication (ElmasonicS30 ® from Elma Schmidbauer GmbH, Singen, Germany).

2.2.2. Core-shell nanocatalyst

A core-shell nanostructure (CS) for this catalyst was achieved in two steps by coating with silica an iron oxide magnetic core obtained by thermal decomposition of organic precursors in organic media, following the protocol described in [23,24]. To form the CS nanocatalyst, 83 mg of iron oxide nanoparticles were dispersed in 300 mL of cyclohexane and placed in a 500 mL flask. Then, 13.3 mL of Igepal were added and mechanically shaken for 30 min. Afterwards, 2.16 mL of ammonium hydroxide were added and shaken for 15 min. Finally, 2.5 mL of TEOS were added (dropwise and by stirring the flask) and the mixture was left for 72 h under mechanical agitation. The obtained product was then washed three times with ethanol and the sample was dispersed in water.

2.2.3. Multicore nanocatalyst

The synthesis of multicore nanocatalysts (MC) was carried out using $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as precursor and ethylene glycol as the solvent in the presence of sodium acetate [25]. For this, a mixture of 40 mL of ethylene glycol, $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.125 M and NaAc 0.5 M were placed in a Teflon lined autoclave. The reaction was carried out inside an oven previously set at 200 °C for 5 h. After this time, the sample was allowed to cool inside the oven (until ≈ 30 °C) and separated by centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was discarded and the precipitated sample was dispersed in water.

2.3. Nanocatalyst characterization

Structural characterization of the samples was performed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), infrared spectroscopy (IR) and elemental analysis. TEM allowed the determination of the mean particle

size, the size distribution, shape and aggregation degree. For this purpose, small drops of the diluted nanocatalyst suspension were deposited on a carbon coated copper grid. A JEM 2100HT JEOL microscope operating at 200 kV was used. At least 200 particles were measured from different micrographs and the data were fitted to a lognormal distribution. XRD was used to determine the crystal structure and crystal size of the samples. The equipment used for XRD was a Siemens D5000 diffractometer and a Panalytical X'pert Powder diffractometer (25 mA, 35 kV) with K- α radiation of Cu ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$). Diffractograms were collected in the 2θ range between 10° and 70° at step width of 0.04° .

The colloidal properties of the nanocatalysts were studied by dynamic light scattering in a Malvern Instrument Zetasizer Nano SZ (Malvern, UK) equipped with a solid-state He-Ne laser ($\lambda = 633 \text{ nm}$). The hydrodynamic diameter was obtained at pH 7 as the average of the size distribution in number (%). The ζ -potential was also measured at different pH values (adjusted with KOH or HNO_3) using $\text{KNO}_3 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ as support electrolyte.

Surface active groups were identified by IR. MIDAC Prospect-IR equipment was used for this purpose. Spectra were recorded in a frequency range between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} . The powder was dispersed in KBr and pressed into pellets. Textural characterization was done by gas adsorption with a surface area analyzer ASAP 2020 from Micromeritics. Prior to the measurements the samples were outgassed at 110°C and $\approx 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Torr}$ for 3 h. The BET surface area was calculated by the BET method in the P/P0 range in which the BET equation shows linear behavior. 0.1620 nm^2 was used as the area occupied by an adsorbed nitrogen molecule. The pore size distribution was calculated from the adsorption branch of the isotherms using the Barrett, Joyner and Halenda (BJH) method for a cylindrical pore model.

Magnetic measurements were performed in a SQUID (Superconducting Quantum Interference Device) Quantum Design XL magnetometer. The Zero Field Cooling (ZFC) susceptibility measurements were carried out by cooling the sample to 2 K in the absence of magnetic field, while field cooling (FC) with the magnetic field on, measuring magnetization up to temperatures of 300 K. In both cases the applied magnetic field was 500 Oe. From this curve, T_b was estimated as a temperature range where magnetisation is maximum and μ_{SP} values were obtained from the maximum superparamagnetic moment in the temperature range corresponding to the linear zone of the inverse susceptibility vs temperature curve. In addition, the magnetization curves were carried out at 5 and 250 K with fields between -5 and 5 T and hysteretic parameters such as saturation magnetisation (M_s) and coercivity (H_c) were calculated. Finally, specific absorption rate (SAR) was estimated from

the initial slope of the heating curves of $1 \text{ mg}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{mL}$ nanocatalysts' suspensions following the methodology described in [22]. The suspensions were placed at the centre of hyperthermia apparatus coil (Fives Celes 12118 M01) and temperature measurements were carried out with an optical probe (OSENSA) at 96 kHz and 202 kHz frequencies and amplitudes from 10 to 60 mT.

2.4. Adsorption and catalytic tests

The adsorption study was carried out using the three prepared nanocatalysts. For this purpose, the absorbance of aqueous solutions of AO8 and MB (100 ppm) was measured after different contact times (5, 15, 30, 60 and 120 min) in the presence of the nanocatalyst (1 mg/mL, 10 mL) and at specific pH values (3, 5 and 9). All adsorption and catalysis tests were performed under mechanical stirring and in closed test tubes to avoid water evaporation during the experiments. The measurements were performed after the separation of the nanocatalysts by magnetic harvesting. Finally, the remnant concentration of AO8 and MB was estimated by measuring the supernatant absorbance and considering the respective calibration curve (Fig. 1). Once the adsorption process was optimized, degradation tests were performed at room temperature, at 90°C and in the presence of an alternating magnetic field (202 kHz, 30 mT, 30 min). The maximum temperature was chosen because in a previous work we demonstrate that increasing the temperature from 60 to 90°C , it is possible to double the degradation at a certain reaction time [26]. For the room temperature tests, 10 mg of nanoparticles were introduced into 10 mL of 100 ppm MB solution and the mixture was kept stirred for 60 min (adsorption equilibrium time). After this time, $100 \mu\text{L}$ of H_2O_2 was added and the absorbance was measured at 5, 15, 30, 60 and 120 min after the addition. The same methodology was followed for the 90°C assays. In both cases two reference targets were used, one containing only the MB solution and another containing the MB solution and $100 \mu\text{L}$ of H_2O_2 . The degradation test in the presence of the alternating magnetic field was carried out using the same proportions of dye, nanoparticles and hydrogen peroxide as in the previous conditions, but, in this case, the effect of the peroxide was evaluated during 30-minute field application (time zero is considered when adding the hydrogen peroxide and applying the magnetic field). After the process, the nanoparticles were magnetically separated and the absorbance of the resulting solutions was measured in order to determine the concentration of MB. Total Organic Concentration (TOC) determination was assessed in the DR890 HACH colorimeter (at a 610 nm wavelength) following method 10173 using Test 'N Tube™

Fig. 1. Calibration curves and molecular structure of the model organic dyes a) acid orange 8 (AO8) and b) methylene blue (MB) both measured at pH = 7 considering that pH variation does not displace the characteristic bands.

Vials (more details are included in the [supporting information](#)).

The amount of iron leached from the nanocatalysts in the final suspensions after the Fenton reaction at 90 °C was measured by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES with a Perkin Elmer apparatus (OPTIME 2100DV, Waltham, MA, USA). In order to check the relevance of the ionic iron leached degradation tests were also conducted using aqueous Fe(II) and Fe(III) chloride solutions at 0.3 ppm concentration under standard conditions (30 min at 90 °C, 100 ppm of dye and 100 μ L of H₂O₂).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Nanocatalysts

TEM images of the as prepared SC, CS and MC nanocatalysts are shown in Fig. 2a-c with their corresponding size distributions fitted to a log-normal function (Fig. 2d-f). In the inset, high resolution images are included showing crystallographic planes corresponding to the spinel structure. Particle size increases from 11 nm for SC to 38 nm for CS (the silica coating is clearly appreciated) and 200 nm for MC. Fig. 2g-i shows the diffraction diagram of the three samples where the same diffraction peaks corresponding to the cubic spinel structure (space group Fd-3 m:227) can be appreciated with crystal sizes of 11, 11 and 20 nm, respectively.

Infrared spectra (Fig. 3a) of the three samples present a common band around 600 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the vibration of the Fe-O bond in the magnetite and at 3500 cm⁻¹ which corresponds to the OH water moieties, while the rest of the bands are related to the different coatings. For the SC sample, the bands corresponding to the symmetric and asymmetric stresses of the carboxylate groups of the citric acid coordinated to the surface of the nuclei are observed (around 1500 cm⁻¹). The CS sample shows an intense band at 1250 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the vibration of the Si-O bond indicating the presence of the silica as confirmed by the TEM images (Fig. 2.b). The spectrum of the MC sample presents the bands (\approx 1600 cm⁻¹) corresponding to the vibration of the C-O-C bond present in the polyethylene glycol on the surface of the nanoparticles [27]. Thermogravimetric analysis (Fig. 3b) exhibited a

common decrease on weight due to the physically adsorbed water present on the samples (below 200 °C). SC presented a decrease of 15% of mass at 500 °C attributed to the organic molecule of citric acid. On the other hand, MC exhibited a small decrease (5%) between 100 and 300 °C due to the presence of some functional groups derived from polyol molecules and an additional 1% over 600 °C attributed to the sintering and transformation of maghemite to hematite, absent in the CS sample.

The surface charge of all the nanocatalysts is negative in a wide pH range larger than 6. Fig. 3c shows that the SC nanoparticles have the present negative ζ -potential through all the pH range due to the ionization of citrate coating. In the case of CS nanoparticles, the isoelectric point (pH at zero charge) was 3.5, as expected for the silica coating, whereas for MC it was around pH 6. The isoelectric point is of paramount importance for the adsorption experiments since at pHs above it the adsorption capacity for positive molecules is maximized whereas the contrary occurs at lower pHs.

The hydrodynamic sizes of the samples at pH around 7 are shown in Table 1 (distribution by number, %) for the different systems together with a summary of their particle and crystal size. These measurements, provide information about the state of aggregation of the particles in the colloid. It can be observed that MC sample presents a higher aggregation with sizes over 1000 nm due to the lack of coating, low surface charge and larger particle size. On the other hand, thanks to the citric acid and silica coating, that provides a shift of the isoelectric point to lower pHs and their small particle size, SC and CS present a lower degree of aggregation with hydrodynamic sizes around 150 nm.

Magnetic properties of the nanocatalysts are summarized in Table 2, including parameters such as saturation magnetization (M_s) and coercivity (H_c). Interestingly, MC nanocatalyst exhibited high M_s values (90 Am²/kg) attributed to their multicore arrangement. Previous studies have shown that these uniform monocrystalline structures have an internal disordered spin arrangement that ease their magnetization when applying external magnetic fields [27]. Within CS nanocatalyst their lower M_s values given by mass of material correspond to the signal decrease due to non-magnetic silica.

Moreover, Fig. 4a shows the magnetic susceptibility versus temperature curves of the samples. The ZFC curves show broad maxima

Fig. 2. Morphological and structural characterization of the Single Core (SC), Core-shell (CS) and Multicore (MC) nanocatalysts: (a-c) TEM images, (d-f) Particle size distributions and (g-i) X-Ray diffraction patterns. Insets in a, b and c show high resolution images of one particle and electron diffraction patterns of a group of particles.

Fig. 3. Surface characterization: Infrared spectra (a), Thermogravimetric Analyses (b) and surface charge as a function of pH (c) for Single core (SC), Core-shell (CS) and Multicore (MC) nanocatalysts.

Table 1

Structural and colloidal parameters of the as prepared nanocatalysts: Nanoparticle size (TEM), hydrodynamic size (DLS) and crystal size (XRD).

Catalyst	TEM size (nm)	Hydrodynamic size (nm)	Crystal size (nm)
SC	11 ± 2	143 (PDI 0.26)	11
CS	38 ± 6	149 (PDI 0.24)	11
MC	198 ± 60	1286 (PDI 0.37)	20

Table 2

Nanocatalysts' magnetic properties obtained from ZFC/FC measurements and magnetization curves at 5 K as described in the experimental section. M_S was calculated by infinite field approximation. μ_{SP} stands for superparamagnetic Bohr magnetons (μ_B).

Nanocatalyst	T_b (K)	M_S^a ($\text{Am}^2/\text{kg Fe}$)	H_c^a (mT)	μ_{SP} (μ_B)
SC	50–150	52.1	22.8	5×10^5
CS	70–250	48.2	21.1	2×10^7
MS	50–300	90.5	30.2	5×10^7

^a Measured at 5 K.

indicating that there is no single blocking temperature but, rather, a range in which the transition to the superparamagnetic regime occurs (see Table 2). This may be due to a broad distribution of nanoparticle sizes or to the existence of interactions between nanoparticles such that several particles behave as a single larger particle. Such particle interactions limit the magnetization imposed by the field and the susceptibility remains constant in the FC branch instead of increasing with decreasing temperature. [28–31].

Furthermore, it can be seen that the susceptibility of the SC nanocatalyst is lower than the one of the MC ones due to spin canting effect

on the surface because of their small particle size [32]. The superparamagnetic moment resulting from the coupling of the moments of the particles that are in the superparamagnetic regime at a certain temperature increases from SC to MC sample, according to the internal structure of the particles and with previous works [33]. Fig. 4b shows the magnetization versus field cycles at 5 K and 250 K, respectively. The magnetization versus applied field curves at 5 K (Fig. 4) indicate ferromagnetic behaviour in all samples with coercive field values between 20 and 30 mT. In all cases, the saturation magnetization values, M_S , are high but lower than those corresponding to the bulk material ($126 \text{ Am}^2/\text{kg Fe}$, [34]), since the magnetization decreases with decreasing particle size due to the canted spin surface layer. The plot at 250 K shows a typical S-shaped cycle corresponding to the behaviour in superparamagnetic regime where no hysteresis cycle is observed. The saturation magnetization values are slightly lower than those at 5 K.

Fig. 4c-e shows the SAR values at different field and frequency values. For the MC system, the highest SAR value ($\approx 4000 \text{ W/g}_{Fe}$) is obtained when operating at 96 kHz and 60 mT and can be attributed to the magnetic cooperative behaviour of the aggregated cores. The heat generation behaviour of the SC and CS systems, lower than those of the MC sample because its lower saturation magnetization and coercivity, are similar because the magnetite cores are of equal size. However, CS nanocatalyst is presented the lower SAR value because the silica coating shields the heat generated by the magnetic cores [33,35–37].

3.2. Adsorption and catalytic measurements

3.2.1. Adsorption tests

SC, CS and MC nanocatalysts were first tested for the adsorption of AO8 and MB considering parameters such as pH and contact time. In the case of the anionic dye AO8, no adsorption was observed at any pH since

Fig. 4. Magnetic characterization of the as prepared nanocatalyst: a) Susceptibility vs temperature, b) Magnetization vs field in T (at 250 K and 5 K) and (c, d, e) Heating efficiency vs field in W/g_{Fe} at different frequencies (96 and 202 kHz).

the surface charge of the nanoparticles (negatively charged) creates a repulsive effect (see Fig. 5a). On the other hand, as MB is a cationic dye, in this case it was possible to achieve higher adsorption efficiencies considering the equilibrium contact time (2 h).

As it can be seen in Fig. 5b, SC and CS nanocatalysts exhibited greater adsorption capacities compared to MC that may be attributed to its larger size and lower specific surface area, 53 m²/g vs. the 80 m²/g of SC and 160 m²/g of CS (N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms and pore size distribution are display in Fig. S2). At pH 9 there is a higher adsorption of the cationic dye MB because the charge on the surface of the nanoparticles is much negative and increases the attraction towards MB. Therefore, it is observed that the more negative the surface charge value is, the greater the amount of dye is adsorbed due to the increase of ionic affinity.

The effect of the contact time was carried out for MB at room temperature and showed that in the case of all three systems, the equilibrium is reached at 5 min (Fig. 5c), with no more variation in the dye concentration after this time. The adsorption capacity of the different

nanoparticles at equilibrium was calculated and appeared to be 16.74, 16.41 and 1.32 mg/g for SC, CS and MC, respectively. Considering this value of equilibrium, the following catalytic tests are performed after 60 min of contact between the catalyst in the dyes' aqueous solution to ensure that adsorption is completed.

3.2.2. Catalytic tests

To analyse the role of adsorption in the degradation of the organic dyes, the degradation was performed at pH 9, where the best adsorption efficiencies were achieved for MB and no adsorption was detected for AO8. During catalytic tests, the degradation of dyes was evaluated by analysing the decolorization and mineralization efficiency. Decolorization of samples can be due to the breaking of the initial molecule into smaller fragments while mineralization is obtained from the total organic carbon transformation into CO₂. Mineralization of MB is shown on Fig. S1 and suggests that a degradation in small fragments rather than mineralization is taking place, as it was observed in the degradation of other molecules by other nanocatalyst [38]. Following the reaction by

Fig. 5. Adsorption efficiency at RT and different pHs of a) acid orange 8 and b) methylene blue. c) methylene blue adsorption as a function of the contact time.

decolourization, it can be concluded that, first of all, the degradation of AO8 was not observed after 180 min for any nanocatalyst at room temperature. However, for MB, degradation at room temperature (Fig. 6a) exhibited very limited efficiencies (<5%) but increased significantly at 90 °C up to 20–40% and 100% (neglecting the adsorption percentage) for MC, CS and SC nanocatalysts, respectively, see Fig. 6b.

These findings about the degradation of MB, demonstrate that adsorption and temperature are fundamental parameters to achieve degradation of the organic compounds using iron oxide nanoparticles. It can be assumed that the adsorbed compound is degraded in the active sites of the nanocatalyst for the later desorption of the degradation product. Therefore, there is a synergistic role between adsorption and degradation, which results in a higher percentage of dye removal and a greater decolourization of the initial solutions. It was also observed that the larger the surface area of the nanocatalysts (SC), the higher the conversion of the organic compounds (up to 100%), in accordance to previous results [40].

On the other hand, without an increase in temperature, the concentration of MB in the supernatant remains practically constant after the addition of hydrogen peroxide (2–5% degradation), indicating that there is no degradation under these conditions. The small difference in favour to CS seems to be due to adsorption on the surface and not to MB degradation due to Fenton process. When the tests were performed at 90 °C, SC nanocatalyst yielded 100% degradation after 180 min of reaction. Interestingly, CS and MC nanocatalysts were less effective under the same conditions in spite of their higher adsorption capacity (Fig. 5). Adsorption is expected to be promoted at 90 °C as a consequence of the chemisorption process, that increases with increasing temperature [41]. However, as the temperature increases, leaching of iron from the nanocatalyst may result in homogeneous catalysis too, and it will be strongly dependant on the nature of the nanoparticle surface. In order to verify that, the iron leaching of the three nanocatalysts at 90 °C for 2 h was measured. The results demonstrated that only SC sample presents a 0.3% of Fe in solution under these conditions. In a separate experiment we confirmed that this amount of iron (used in the form of Fe chloride) resulted to be enough to degrade the dye in similar extent than with the SC nanocatalyst. It means that for this sample, homogeneous catalysis is taking place together with the heterogeneous process. On the contrary, CS and MC samples present no leaching detectable by ICP showing its efficiency as pure heterogeneous catalysts and consequently, no degradation is expected after adsorption/desorption cycles. However, for SC sample, reusability and recyclability is expected to be limited due to the Fe leaching. Previous work on similar nanoparticles showed that after four cycles, catalytic efficiency was preserved over 80% [42].

Kinetic analysis of the degradation process gives information about

whether the catalytic process is going through a Fenton or Fenton-like reaction [39]. Fenton reactions performed mainly by the presence of Fe^{2+} are usually described by a pseudo-second order kinetic model, while Fenton-like (mainly performed by Fe^{3+}) by a pseudo-first order model. Fig. S3 exhibits the linear adjustments to the mentioned models considering all three samples and the kinetic parameters are listed in Table S1. A catalytic reaction of order one is observed for SC sample, suggesting that MB molecules degrade mainly due to the action of Fe^{3+} in a Fenton-like reaction, pointing out to a synergistic action of homogeneous and heterogeneous catalytic processes due to Fe leaching. However, CS and MC do not present a very large R^2 value for order 1 or 2, suggesting a degradation of MB by the joint action of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} ions, the latter from the nanoparticle surface.

Finally, the effect of performing the degradation reaction under an alternating magnetic field (200 kHz, 30 mT, 30 min) was assessed using the nanocatalysts (Fig. 6.c). For this purpose, the reaction started together with the ignition of the field and without allowing the media to heat up, like in the above-mentioned assays at 90 °C. Interestingly, the degradation efficiencies were improved in almost 50% respect to the test at room temperature. This increase in the reaction yields can be attributed to the surface temperature of the nanocatalysts that with the AMF can instantly heat up since in the short reaction time there was not a significant increase of the media temperature. Recently, it has been demonstrated that temperatures up to 90 °C can be easily attained tuning magnetic anisotropy of the particles and field conditions [43].

4. Conclusions

To eliminate organic pollutants from wastewater is of the outmost importance as there are now severe environmental policies centred in reducing and controlling these hazardous compounds. Here, heterogeneous Fenton reactions were performed using different iron oxide based nanocatalysts to understand how the adsorption influence this process. It was possible to prove that anionic dye acid orange 8 presents electrostatic repulsion towards all catalysts due to their surface charges, while cationic methylene blue exhibited great affinity with much higher adsorption capacities. Surface and the degree of internal and external defects play an important role in the catalytic activity. Single core nanocatalyst having the smallest size, the largest surface area and lower crystallinity for being synthesised at low temperature, present the highest percentage of dye degradation. However, multicore nanocatalysts, with the largest nanoparticles and high crystallinity for being synthesised at higher temperatures, present lower catalytic activity. Interestingly, only the loaded catalysts degraded these organic compounds by the advanced oxidation process. Therefore, it can be concluded that for the reaction to occur is necessary first the adsorption

Fig. 6. Degradation of methylene blue a) at room temperature and b) at 90 °C (10 mg of nanocatalysts in 10 mL of 100 ppm MB solution and 100 μL of hydrogen peroxide were used). c) Degradation of methylene blue as a function of temperature (25 and 90 °C) using the magnetic nanocatalysts and under an alternating magnetic field (200 kHz, 30 mT, 30 min).

of the reactants that will degrade on the surface of the catalysts to finally desorb the products. Furthermore, and even though homogeneous Fenton reaction exhibited large efficiencies, here it was also proved that considerable yields are possible with heterogeneous catalysis when protecting the iron oxide core from leaching (eg. with a silica coating). This is an important step forward to fully understand the advanced oxidation process using magnetic nanocatalysts and to take it to industrial facilities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

C.D.-U. and A.G.-C contributed equally to this work: methodology, validation, visualization, formal analysis, data curation, writing-original draft preparation, writing-review and editing; L.S.: methodology, validation, formal analysis; M.J.T.F, R.S. and S.V.V.: methodology, validation, formal analysis, writing-review and editing; M.P.M. conceptualization, resources, investigation, funding acquisition, writing-original draft preparation, writing-review and editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.130695](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.130695).

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